

AN OPEN-LABEL CLINICAL STUDY ON THE EFFICACY OF *GODANTI BHASMA WITH PATHYADI KWATHA* IN THE MANAGEMENT OF *ARDHAVABHEDAKA* (MIGRAINE)

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Migraine is a primary headache disorder characterized by recurrent attacks of a specific type of pain in one half of the head. The prevalence of Migraine in India is found to be around 26%. Migraine has a significant negative impact on sufferers' ability to work, engage in social activities, and maintain a family life. Patients who are treated with contemporary medicine have undesirable side effects or are hesitant to take medication and do not react to conventional therapy. According to Ayurvedic classics, signs and symptoms of *Ardhavabhedaka* (a type of *Shiroroga*) can be correlated with Migraine. Considering the limited availability of conventional medicine treatment options, this study was conducted. *Godanti bhasma* is used in various types of headaches, whereas *Pathyadi Kwatha* is indicated in the management of *Shiroroga*. **Objective:** To evaluate the efficacy of *Godanti bhasma* with *Pathyadi kwatha* in the management of *Ardhavabhedaka* (Migraine). **Materials and Methods:** It is an open-label single-arm clinical study. Setting: Shreeyash

Ayurved Hosp., Chh. Sambhajinagar. 20 diagnosed patients of migraine were randomly selected from OPD & IPD. The selected subjects were administered *Shamana Therapy*, comprising *Godanti Bhasma* (125 mg) and *Pathyadi Kwatha* (15 ml), twice a day after meals,

for 60 days. **Discussion:** Based on the assessment criteria, the data were graded, and the results were analyzed statistically. **Results:** The outcome of the treatment was found to be statistically significant in 20 patients after 2 months of the treatment.

KEYWORDS: Migraine, *Ardhavabhedaka*, *Shiroroga*, *Godanti bhamsa*, *Pathyadi Kwatha*.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda considers the *Shira* to be foremost among all organs as it is the region of the body where the vital parts like *Prana* and all the *Indriya* (senses) of a living being are located. It is *Uttama* (vital) amongst all the other organs of the body, therefore known as *Uttamanga*.^[1 & 2] *Acharya Charaka* has mentioned *Shira* under *Trimarma* and *Dashapranayatana*, so it is essential to safeguard this region from any serious diseases.^[3 & 4] *Shiroroga* (Diseases of the head) can be correlated with headache in modern science. A person's quality of life is affected when they experience any kind of headache. The long-term effort of coping with a chronic headache disorder may also predispose the individual to other illnesses. Usually, a headache is a common neurological entity in society. It may manifest as a primary headache syndrome like migraine, tension-type headache, or cluster headache, or secondary headache due to a variety of illnesses.^[5] Primary headache disorders are among the most ubiquitous disorders, affecting people in all countries.^[6] India appears to be no exception.^[7]

Due to rapid changes in lifestyle, stressful and competitive times, headache disorders are extraordinarily common and, if neglected, may lead to many serious complications. These etiological factors vitiate *Vata Dosha*, which further affects other *Doshas* and then the *Rakta Dhatu* in the head region, leading to various types of *Shiroroga* with multiple symptoms. *Ardhavabhedaka* is one of such *Shiroroga*.

Acharya Charaka, *Sushruta*, and *Vagbhata* have mentioned *Ardhavabhedaka Shiroroga*. 'Ardha' means half, and 'Bhedaka' means cutting or churning type of pain. So, when there is cutting or churning type of pain in the half of the head region, specifically the carotid region, eyebrow, temple, ear, eye, and forehead, it is called 'Ardhavabhedaka'. The main involved *Dosha* is either *Vata* or *Vata-Kapha*.^[8] *Acharya Sushruta* says this pain is violent and excruciatingly piercing in nature due to the involvement of *Tridosha*.^[9] While *Acharya Vagbhata* further adds that as the disease progresses, it damages the senses of the ear, eye, and also destroys the intellect. *Acharya Vagbhata* considers the involvement of only *Vata Dosha* in the pathogenesis.^[10]

The modern entity that resembles *Ardhavabhedaka* is 'Migraine'. The Global Burden of Disease study 2010 found Migraine to be the 3rd most prevalent disorder and 7th highest specific cause of disability worldwide.^[11] The management of Migraine varies from simple analgesics, NSAIDs, 5-HT Receptor agonists, Dihydroergotamine, Metoclopramide, to Prochlorperazine.^[12] The long-term use of these medications is known for a variety of adverse events with limited efficacy.^[13]

In Ayurveda, *Godanti Bhasma* is referred to be useful in *Shiroroga chikitsa* (Management of the diseases of the head).^[14&15] Whereas *Pathyadi Kwatha* (decoction) is mentioned in *Sharangdhara Samhita*, especially in the management of *Shiroroga*.^[16] Further it is also being widely practiced to manage *Shiroroga*.^[17] In view of the above factors, an effort has been made in this study to assess the therapeutic efficacy of *Godanti Bhasma* and *Pathyadi Kwatha* in the management of *Ardhavabhedaka*.

OBJECTIVE

To evaluate the efficacy of *Godanti bhasma* with *Pathyadi kwatha* in the management of *Ardhavabhedaka* (Migraine)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Type of study: Open-label single-arm clinical study.

Sample selection: In the present study, 20 diagnosed patients with *Ardhavabhedaka* (migraine) were selected from the OPD and IPD of *Kayachikitsa* Department of Shreeyash Ayurved Hosp., Chh. Sambhajinagar. The diagnosis was made on the following criteria.

* Minimum 5 episodes of headache in half of the head in history, either random episodes or with specific intervals.

* Headache episode lasting for 3 to 36 hours.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients fulfilling the diagnostic criteria.
2. Patients of 16 to 70 years of age, irrespective of gender and socioeconomic status.
3. Patients willing to participate and provide consent were included.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Referred pain in one half of the head due to a disorder of the eye, ear, nose, throat, or teeth.

2. Patients suffering from diabetes, tuberculosis, hypertension, malignancy, any other general debilitating health condition, needing surgical intervention (polyp, etc.), or patients who were on any other medications that may interfere with trial treatment.

Intervention

Drug: *Godanti Bhasma* and the contents of the *Pathyadi Kwatha* were procured from a GMP-certified company.

Table no. 1: showing the properties of *Godanti Bhasma*.^[18]

Sr. No.	Category	Details
1	<i>Rasa</i>	<i>Madhura, Kashaya</i>
2	<i>Guna</i>	<i>Sukshma, Mrudu</i>
3	<i>Virya</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>
4	<i>Vipaka</i>	<i>Madhura</i>
5	<i>Karma</i>	<i>Shirahshoolahara, Jvaraghna, Kshayahara, Kasahara, Balya</i>

Table no. 2: showing the contents and properties of *Pathyadi kwatha*.^[19]

S N	Name	Latin name	<i>Rasa</i>	<i>Guna</i>	<i>Virya</i>	<i>Vipaka</i>	<i>Karma</i>
1	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula, Retz.</i>	<i>Lavanavarjit Kashaya pradhana pancharasa</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Agnimandyahara, Krumighna, Deepana, Pachana</i>
2	<i>Bibhitaki</i>	<i>Terminalia belerica, Roxb.</i>	<i>Kashaya</i>	<i>Ruksha, Laghu</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Kaphavataghna. Trishnahara, Rasa-Rakta-Mamsa-Medorogahara</i>
3	<i>Amalaki</i>	<i>Emblia officinalis, Phyllanthus emblica, Linn.</i>	<i>Lavavarjita pancharasa amlapradhana</i>	<i>Guru, Ruksha, Sheeta</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Kaphaghna, Dipana</i>
4	<i>Bhunimba</i>	<i>Andrographis paniculata Burm.</i>	<i>Tikta, Kashya</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Jvaraghna, Shophahara, Tridoshashamaka, Kledaghna, Krumighna, Yakrututtejaka, Raktaprasadana</i>
5	<i>Haridra</i>	<i>Curcuma longa, Linn</i>	<i>Tikta, Katu</i>	<i>Ruksha, Laghu</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Lekhanatridoshaghna, krumighna, mehanashaka, vishodh</i>
6	<i>Nimba</i>	<i>Azadirachta indica A. Juss.</i>	<i>Tikta, Kashaya</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Sheeta</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Krumigha, Kledaghna, Jvaraghna, Dahashamaka,</i>

							<i>Raktaprasadana, Kushthaghna, Tridoshashamaka</i>
7	<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Tinospora cordifolia (Willd.) Miers</i>	<i>Tikta, Kashaya (with Madhura anurasa)</i>	<i>Laghu, Snigdha</i>	<i>Ushṇa</i>	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Tridoṣaghna, Rasayana, Jvaraghna, Dipana-Pachana, Raktaprasadana</i>

Case taking: A detailed case history was obtained for each patient to identify triggering etiological factors related to dietary habits, bowel habits, sleep patterns, stress and workload, and menstrual history.

Vitals examination – Pulse, temperature, blood pressure, respiration, and general examination of the eye, ear, nose, throat, head, and oral cavity was done before initiating the treatment.

Dose: *Godanti Bhasma* was administered in a dose of 125 mg along with 15 ml of *Pathyadi Kwatha* as an *anupana*.

The decoction (*Kwatha*) was prepared according to the classical procedure described in the *Sharangadhara Samhita, Madhyama Khaṇḍa*. The patient was given 7.5 g coarse powder of *Pathyadi kwatha* and instructed to add 120 mL of potable water. The mixture was heated over a moderate flame and brought to gentle boiling until the volume was reduced to one-eighth of the original quantity, i.e., 15 mL. After cooling, it was filtered with a clean muslin cloth and administered fresh.

Time of intake: Two times a day – once in the morning and once in the evening - on an empty stomach.

Duration: 60 days.

Follow-up: 15 days, 30 days, 45 days, and 60 days.

Pathya-Apathya- Patients were counseled to follow regular meal times, get sufficient sleep, and avoid foods or activities known to trigger headache episodes, in accordance with Ayurvedic principles of *Nidanaparivarjana*.

Diet restrictions: Bakery products, Spicy, oily, curdy products, fermented foods, and stale foods were prohibited.

Assessment Criteria: Headache intensity and associated disability were assessed using validated tools.

1. The Migraine Severity (MIGSEV)^[20] scale was employed to evaluate the overall severity of migraine attacks based on four dimensions: intensity of pain, disability in daily activities, tolerability, and associated symptoms.
2. MIDAS Scale^[21] - Headache-related functional impairment was measured using the Migraine Disability Assessment (MIDAS) Questionnaire, a five-item instrument assessing the impact of migraine on work, school, household, and social activities over the preceding three months. Total MIDAS scores were calculated by summing responses to all items and categorized into four grades: Grade I (0–5, little or no disability), Grade II (6–10, mild disability), Grade III (11–20, moderate disability), and Grade IV (≥ 21 , severe disability)
3. Other symptoms assessed were photophobia, phonophobia, vertigo, and neck stiffness.

OBSERVATIONS

The mean age of the patients was 38 years, with an observed range of 25 to 52 years, indicating that the study population primarily consisted of middle-aged adults.

Table no. 3: showing the gender-wise distribution of the patients.

Sr. No.	Gender	(n = 20)	%
1	Male	4	20%
2	Female	16	80%

Out of the 20 participants enrolled in the study, 4 (20%) were male and 16 (80%) were female, indicating a predominance of female participants in the study population.

Table no. 4: showing triggering factors of Migraine.

Sr. No.	Triggering factors	No. of Patients
1	Missing regular meal time	12
2	Recent h/o Journey	13
3	After a Specific type of food eating	09
4	Deprived of night's sleep	08
5	Sniffing a specific smell	05
6	Excessive screen watching	05
7	Exposure to sunlight	05
8	Before menstruation	02

Among the patients assessed, several triggering factors for headache episodes were identified. Missing regular meal times was reported by 12 patients, while a recent history of travel was noted by 13 patients. Nine patients experienced headaches after consuming specific types of

food. Sleep deprivation, particularly missing a full night's sleep, was reported by 8 patients. Sniffing particular smells and excessive screen exposure were each identified as triggers by 5 patients. Similarly, exposure to strong sunlight precipitated headaches in 5 patients. Additionally, 2 female patients reported headache episodes occurring before menstruation.

Table no. 5: showing *Dosha* involved in the etiopathogenesis of *Ardhavabhedaka*.

Sr. No.	<i>Dosha</i> Predominance	No. of patients	%
1	<i>Vata Pitta</i> Predominance	09	45%
2	<i>Pitta</i> Predominance	05	25%
3	<i>Vata</i> Predominance	03	15%
4	<i>Vata Kapha</i> Predominance	02	10%
5	<i>Kapha</i> Predominance	01	5%

The distribution of *Dosha* dominance among the study participants with *Ardhavabhedaka* (migraine) revealed a clear predominance of *Vata–Pitta prakruti*, which was observed in 9 patients (45%). This was followed by *Pitta* predominance in 5 patients (25%) and *Vata* predominance in 3 patients (15%). A smaller proportion of patients exhibited *Vata–Kapha* predominance, accounting for 2 cases (10%), while *Kapha* predominance was least common, seen in only 1 patient (5%). Overall, these findings indicate a higher involvement of *Vata* and *Pitta doshas* in patients suffering from *Ardhavabhedaka* (migraine), supporting the Ayurvedic concept of *Vata–Pitta* predominance in the etiopathogenesis of this disorder.

RESULTS

Table no. 6: showing the effect of the treatment on the MIDAS Score in patients of *Ardhavabhedaka* (Migraine) assessed by Paired t-test (n=20).

Parameter	BT (Mean SD)	AT (Mean SD)	Mean Difference	T value	P value
MIDAS Score	13.10±2.79	5.00±2.34	8.10	10.00	<0.001

The MIDAS score showed a highly significant reduction following treatment in patients of *Ardhavabhedaka* (migraine). The mean MIDAS score decreased from 13.10 ± 2.79 at baseline to 5.00 ± 2.34 after treatment, with a mean difference of 8.10. Statistical analysis using the paired *t*-test revealed this improvement to be highly significant ($t = 10.00$, $df = 19$, $p < 0.001$), indicating a marked reduction in migraine-related disability following the intervention.

Table no. 7: showing the effect of the treatment on the MIGSEV Score in patients of *Ardhavabhedaka* (Migraine) assessed by the Wilcoxon signed rank test (n=20).

Sr. No.	MIGSEV Parameter	BT Mean	AT Mean	Z value	P value
1	Intensity of pain	2.30	1.06	4.62	<0.05
2	Tolerability	1.75	0.65	3.51	<0.05
3	Disability/Inactivity	1.62	0.76	3.38	<0.05
4	Nausea	1.56	0.92	3.20	<0.05

Assessment of migraine severity using the MIGSEV scale demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in all evaluated parameters following treatment in patients with *Ardhavabhedaka* (migraine). The intensity of pain showed a marked reduction, with the mean score decreasing from 2.30 at baseline to 1.06 after treatment, a statistically significant difference as determined by the Wilcoxon signed-rank test ($Z = 4.62, p < 0.05$). Similarly, tolerability improved significantly, as reflected by a reduction in mean score from 1.75 to 0.65 ($Z = 3.51, p < 0.05$). A significant decrease was also observed in disability/inactivity, with mean scores reducing from 1.62 to 0.76 ($Z = 3.38, p < 0.05$). Furthermore, nausea, a common associated symptom of migraine, showed a statistically significant reduction from 1.56 at baseline to 0.92 after treatment ($Z = 3.20, p < 0.05$). Overall, the significant improvement across all MIGSEV parameters indicates a substantial reduction in migraine severity following the intervention.

Table No. 8: Effect of treatment on associated symptoms of *Ardhavabhedaka* (Migraine) assessed by the Wilcoxon signed rank test (n = 20)

Sr. No.	Symptom	BT Mean	AT Mean	Z vaue	P value
1	Neck stiffness	2.08	1.12	4.10	<0.05
2	Photophobia	1.62	0.76	3.38	<0.05
3	Phonophobia	2.30	1.06	4.62	<0.05
4	Vertigo	1.75	0.65	3.51	<0.05

All associated symptoms showed a statistically significant reduction after the treatment. Neck stiffness showed a marked decrease in mean score from 2.08 before treatment (BT) to 1.12 after treatment (AT) ($Z = 4.10, p < 0.05$). Photophobia was significantly reduced, with the mean score declining from 1.62 to 0.76 ($Z = 3.38, p < 0.05$). Similarly, phonophobia demonstrated a significant improvement, with mean values decreasing from 2.30 to 1.06 ($Z = 4.62, p < 0.05$). Vertigo also showed a statistically significant reduction, with mean scores reduced from 1.75 to 0.65 after treatment ($Z = 3.51, p < 0.05$). Overall, the findings indicate that the treatment was effective in significantly alleviating the associated symptoms of *Ardhavabhedaka*.

DISCUSSION

Ayurveda classics mention *Ardhavabhedaka* as a *Vata-Pitta* predominant *Tridoshaja* disorder of the head, marked by pricking, throbbing, and unilateral pain due to vitiated *Vata*. Burning, redness, irritability, nausea, vomiting, and photophobia are due inflammatory response due to *Pitta dosha* vitiation. Vitiated *Vata* mixes with *Pitta* Dosha, causing acute and penetrating pain. Other vascular and neurological disturbances are due to the involvement of the *Shiromarma*. The channels in the *Shirasrotas* become inflamed, narrowed, and hyperreactive, leading to unilateral attacks.

In the present open-label clinical study, the mean age of the patients was 38 years, with an age range of 25 to 52 years, indicating that *Ardhavabhedaka* (*migraine*) predominantly affected middle-aged adults. This age distribution aligns with contemporary epidemiological data on migraine, which report peak prevalence during the most productive years of life, thereby exerting a substantial impact on functional capacity and quality of life.^[22] From an Ayurvedic perspective, this age group corresponds to the *Madhyama Vaya*, a phase characterized by physiological predominance of *Pitta* along with active *Vata* functions, rendering individuals more susceptible to *Vata-Pitta* disorders such as *Ardhavabhedaka*.

A marked female predominance (80%) was observed in this study population, with only 20% male participants. This finding is consistent with global migraine literature, which consistently reports higher prevalence in females.^[23] This gender difference may be attributed to hormonal fluctuations, menstrual cycle-related *Apana Vata* disturbances, and *Pitta* vitiation during *Rajahkala*. Additionally, factors such as emotional stress, irregular dietary patterns, and sleep disturbances—more commonly reported among women—may further predispose them to *Shirogata Vata-Pitta Vikaras*. The presence of menstruation-related headache episodes in some female participants further supports the role of hormonal and *Doshika* influences in the manifestation of migraine.^[24&25]

In this study, Analysis of triggering factors revealed that lifestyle-related and environmental stimuli played a significant role in precipitating headache episodes. Recent history of travel (65%) and missing regular meal times (60%) were the most frequently reported triggers. Travel, particularly involving irregular routines, sleep disruption, and physical strain, is known to aggravate *Vata Dosha*, while missing meals leads to *Vata-Pitta* provocation. Consumption of specific foods (45%), likely possessing *Ushna*, *Amla*, or *Vidahi* properties, further contributes to *Pitta* aggravation.^[26]

Sleep deprivation reported by 40% of patients is a well-recognized factor for Vata Dosha vitiation, which may have acted as a priming mechanism that lowers neurological tolerance thresholds, as sleep disruption and poor sleep quality are closely associated with migraine susceptibility and sensory dysregulation. Scientific evidence shows that sleep disturbances and poor sleep quality are commonly associated with migraine, and lack of adequate sleep can increase susceptibility to migraine attacks.^[27] Sensory triggers, including exposure to strong smells, excessive screen exposure, and sunlight, each affecting 25% of patients, indicate neurovascular and trigemino-vascular hyper-reactivity characteristic of patients with migraine.^[28&29] According to Ayurveda, *Shira* is a seat of *Praṇa Vata*, *Alochaka Pitta*, and *Tarpaka Kapha*, where even mild sensory insults can precipitate pain in a predisposed individual.

The assessment of *Doṣha* predominance revealed that *Vata–Pitta* dominance (45%) was the most common etiological pattern, followed by *Pitta* dominance (25%) and *Vata* dominance (15%). The relatively lower prevalence of *Kapha* involvement further reinforces the classical Ayurvedic view that *Ardhavabhedaka* can be primarily considered as a *Vata–Pitta Pradhana Vyadhi*.

In the present clinical evaluation, the combined use of *Godanti Bhasma* and *Pathyadi Kwatha* resulted in a significant improvement in both migraine severity and migraine-related disability in patients with *Ardhavabhedaka*.

Furthermore, in Ayurvedic therapeutics, *Nidana-parivarjana*^[30] (the avoidance of causative factors) remains the foremost principle of management. Careful elicitation of patient history allowed identification of specific dietary, lifestyle, and triggers responsible for *Vata–Pitta* aggravation. Patients were counselled to follow regular meal times, ensure adequate sleep, and avoid triggering factors identified during case evaluation. Strict adherence to these measures not only mitigates recurrent *Doṣha prakopa* but also enhances the efficacy of *Shamana* therapies by reducing continuous provocation of pathological processes.

The statistically significant reduction observed in all MIGSEV parameters reflects effective control over pain intensity, associated symptoms, and attack tolerability. The marked decline in the MIDAS score and associated symptoms indicates a substantial improvement in functional capacity and day-to-day activities.

Godanti is a source of natural calcium existing in the form of calcium sulphate, which has cooling, antacid, anti-inflammatory, and astringent properties.^[31] *Godanti bhasma* possesses *Sheeta Virya* (cooling potency) directly helps in reducing *Pitta*. It has a *Madhura Vipaka* and *Snigdha Guṇa*, which pacify *Vata* through the *anulomana* effect, and traditional *Tridosha-hara* properties help in calming both *Vata* and *Pitta* simultaneously. Recent studies have highlighted that *bhasmas* possess the capability to target drug delivery to specific sites in the body with fewer side effects.^[32] Thus, *Godanti Bhasma* directly worked as *Shirashoolahara* due to the target drug delivery capability.

On the other hand, *Pathyadi Kwatha* demonstrated a meaningful reduction in the clinical severity and frequency of *Ardhavabhedaka* attacks, suggesting a therapeutic effect consistent with its classical indications. It contains multiple herbal drugs. *Haritaki* and *Amalaki* have a *Vata-shamana* effect. *Nimba*, *Bhunimba*, and *Musta* alleviate *Pitta*. *Haritaki* and *Bibhitaki* prevent *srotorodha* via the *Anulomana* effect. The *Amapachana* and *Deepana* effect of *Musta*, *Guduchi*, *Bhunimba*, and *Haritaki* break the root of *Dosha-Prakopa* and restore proper *Agni*.

Guduchi is known for its immunomodulatory, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, neuroprotective, and antistress activities.^[33&34] Evidence-based pharmacological actions of *Musta* showed anti-inflammatory, analgesic, and antioxidant properties, supporting the fact that it helped in relieving the pain in *Ardhavabhedaka*.^[35] *Guduchi* and *Amalaki* are *Rasayana* and *Medhya* drugs. They collectively improve the resistance to triggers like stress, hunger, and sleep disturbances. The observed improvement in headache intensity, burning sensations, and associated gastrointestinal or sensory symptoms may be attributed to the *Pitta*-pacifying and anti-inflammatory constituents such as *Nimba*, *Bhunimba*, *Guduchi*, and *Musta*. Classical Ayurvedic texts describe *Bibhitaki* as *Shirorogahara*, *Kanṭhya*, and *Kaphanissaraka*. *Acharya Sushruta* describes *Bibhitaki* as *Kaphamedohara* and useful in diseases of the head and throat, implying its efficacy in *Srotorodha-janya Shiro-roga*.^[36]

Haridra (turmeric) has been used in the Ayurvedic tradition since antiquity for its well-recognized analgesic, anti-inflammatory, and *Krimighna* (antimicrobial/antibiotic) properties.^[37&38] It exerts *Shotha-hara*, *Vedana-sthapana*, and *Raktaprasadana* actions, thereby aiding in the alleviation of unilateral throbbing pain, associated nausea, and sensory hypersensitivity. Similarly, *Bhunimba* possesses *Shotha-hara*, *Jvaraghna*, *Vedana-sthapana*, and *Raktagata Dosha-shamana* actions, thus playing a supportive role in alleviating

symptoms. Experimental animal studies have demonstrated its anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, analgesic, and antihypertensive activities.^[39]

Consequently, owing to properties such as *Tridoshaghna*, particularly *Vatapittahara*, *Vedanasthapan*, *Shothahar*, and *Rasayana*, the administration of *Godanti Bhasma* in conjunction with *Pathyadi kwatha* yielded promising outcomes in patients with *Ardhambhedaka*.

Ethical Clearance: This topic of study, together with the case proforma, was submitted to the IEC of Shreeyash Ayurvedic College, Chh. Sambhajinagar. The significance, objectives, methodology, and probable results of the study were clarified to the committee, and ethical clearance was obtained for the conduction of the study.

Informed consent: All 20 patients were informed about the study, and written consent was obtained.

CONCLUSION

The present open-label clinical study concludes that *Godanti Bhasma* (125 mg) combined with *Pathyadi Kwatha* (15 ml) administered for 60 days is found to be effective in the management of *Ardhambhedaka* (Migraine). Statistically significant improvement was observed in migraine severity and disability, which are clearly reflected by reductions in MIGSEV and MIDAS scores along with associated symptoms such as photophobia, phonophobia, vertigo, and neck stiffness.

This therapeutic outcome can be attributed to the combined strategy, where *Shamana* therapy was complemented by *Nidana-parivarjana*. The intervention was well tolerated, suggesting that *Godanti Bhasma* with *Pathyadi Kwatha*, supported by lifestyle modification and trigger avoidance, is a safe and effective Ayurvedic option for migraine management, warranting further evaluation through larger controlled studies.

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